

PERIFORMANCE
Science with Society for Mission Cancer

D7.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Funded by
the European Union

Project name	PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT IN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES FOR MISSION CANCER: MANAGING COMPLEXITY OF EMERGING TECHNOLOGIES
Project acronym	PERIFORMANCE
Grant number	101216808
Deliverable no	D7.1
Milestone title	Data Management Plan
Contractual delivery month	M6
Responsible partner	BBMRI-ERIC
Author(s)	Melanie Goisaufl
Task no and Title	T7.1: Project, Risk, and Quality Management
Submission date	2026-02-27
Dissemination level	PU

DOCUMENT LOG

Version	Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Comment	Author/partner
V1.0	2026-01-31	First draft	Melanie Goisauf, Agnieszka Kosciuszko
V1.1	2026-02-27	Reviewed version	Melanie Goisauf

ABBREVIATIONS

Term	Description
PERIFORMANCE	Public Engagement in Research Infrastructures for Mission Cancer: Managing Complexity of Emerging Technologies
DMP	Data Management Plan, i.e. the present document.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. This acronym identifies a set of properties scientific data assets should possess to enable reproducible research and thus to be relevant to the research community.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation, the EU law that establishes the legal framework for personal data management
WP	Work Package, a team of experts handling a set of related activities in the project

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes **Version 1.1 of the PERIFORMANCE Data Management Plan (DMP)**. It outlines the categories of data generated and processed within the consortium and describes the measures implemented to ensure compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), in line with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement and Programme Guide.

PERIFORMANCE enhances stakeholder engagement in cancer research by leveraging the federated biobanking domain as a focal point for transdisciplinary research and innovation. Adopting a quadruple helix approach—engaging patients and donors, research and healthcare professionals, industry partners, and policymakers—the project contributes to the objectives of EU Mission: Cancer. It addresses ethical, legal, and societal aspects of emerging sociotechnical transformations, including the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) in cancer biobanking.

In this context, the DMP identifies and governs three main categories of data handled by the consortium:

1. Metadata and service-related data generated through project coordination and dissemination activities;
2. Application and consortium administrative data, including open call submissions and internal management documentation;
3. Research output data generated through qualitative and quantitative empirical research activities.

For each category, the DMP defines procedures for secure handling, storage, access control, preservation, and, where applicable, public dissemination. Secure access is addressed proportionately, taking into account the different levels of sensitivity and granularity of the managed data.

PERIFORMANCE fully complies with the Open Science policy of Horizon Europe and integrates Open Science practices across its methodologies, deliverables, publications, guidelines, and non-restricted datasets. The consortium recognises the central role of Open Science in enhancing research quality, transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. Mandatory and recommended Open Science practices are embedded within the project's methodological framework and are regularly reviewed during coordination and monitoring activities.

Access to research outputs follows the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.” The project promotes broad sharing and reuse of results while ensuring full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), national legislation, ethical approvals, confidentiality obligations, and intellectual property considerations.

To support Open Science implementation, PERIFORMANCE will:

- Deposit research outputs and metadata in trusted, OpenAIRE-compliant repositories;

- Provide guidance and support to participants to ensure effective compliance with Open Access and Open Data requirements.

The DMP provides a comprehensive overview of the data generated and collected during the project, including their origin, types, formats, purposes, and access conditions. It further specifies storage solutions, curation procedures, long-term preservation strategies, indicative timelines, allocated resources, and quality assurance measures. Clear responsibilities for data management are defined across work packages to ensure consistency and accountability within the consortium.

The DMP is a **living document**. It will be updated throughout the project lifecycle and revised prior to project completion to reflect the final status of data generation, sharing, and preservation arrangements. Through this structured and adaptive approach, PERIFORMANCE ensures that its data management practices maximise scientific value and societal impact while safeguarding ethical standards and legal compliance.

2.DATA SUMMARY

2.1.General Description of the Data

PERIFORMANCE will generate and process three main categories of data throughout its implementation:

1. **Consortium and administrative data**, required for project management, coordination, reporting, communication, and dissemination.
2. **Open call application data**, collected and processed in the context of open calls implemented within the project.
3. **Research data**, generated through qualitative and quantitative empirical research activities on stakeholder engagement in cancer biobanking and governance.
4. **Communication, dissemination and participatory activity data** for dissemination and training activities.

In addition, the project will re-use publicly available scientific literature, policy documents, and existing engagement and biobanking governance frameworks for desk research purposes. Public datasets relevant to cancer research governance and stakeholder engagement may also be consulted. No personal or restricted third-party datasets will be re-used unless full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and applicable national legislation is ensured.

Data generation and re-use directly support the project objectives, namely:

- Identifying stakeholder preferences for engagement strategies;
- Analysing the implementation of bottom-up engagement practices in cancer research and biobanking;
- Evaluating inclusivity, contextual relevance, and transferability of engagement models;
- Developing evidence-based policy and governance recommendations.

In line with the mandatory Open Science requirements under Horizon Europe, all data and outputs will be managed in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). Data will be made available following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,” subject to legal, ethical, confidentiality, and intellectual property constraints.

2.2.Consortium and Administrative Data

Administrative and consortium data are generated in the context of project coordination and management. These data include:

- Contact details of consortium members, collaborators, and open call evaluators (e.g., names, affiliations, professional email addresses);

- Agendas, meeting minutes, internal reports, milestone drafts, and working documents;
- Periodic technical and financial reports containing author names and affiliations;
- Public deliverables (.pdf) containing author names and affiliations;
- Scientific publications (Open Access, .pdf) containing author names and affiliations;
- Conference abstracts and workshop contributions;
- Communication and dissemination materials, including newsletters, website content (HTML/text), photographs (.jpg/.png), and webinar recordings (.mp4).

These data originate from routine project management and communication activities carried out by consortium partners.

Internal administrative documents and personal contact data are confidential and will not be made publicly accessible. Public deliverables and scientific publications will be made available in compliance with Horizon Europe Open Access requirements. Administrative personal data will be processed in accordance with the applicable institutional privacy framework and GDPR.

2.3. Open Call Application Data

PERIFORMANCE includes the implementation of open calls for engagement activities aimed at empowering local communities to actively participate in research, fostering new methodologies that integrate citizens and patients into the research process, and promoting the inclusive and ethical integration of AI and EHDS. The application process entails the collection and processing of personal and project-related data submitted by applicants.

The application form collects mandatory information including:

- Applicant's first and last name;
- Email address and affiliation;
- Applicant institution and institutional address;
- Names, affiliations, and roles of partners involved in the proposal;
- Description of the proposed engagement activity;
- Expected outcomes and impact;
- Identification of potential risks, including ethical and societal implications, and proposed mitigation measures;
- Budget table and justification of requested funding;
- Ethics approval checklist.

Applications may also include personal data of co-applicants. Applicants are required to ensure that individuals named in the proposal have provided consent for their personal data to be included in the application.

Application data are processed by the responsible work package team and shared with independent evaluators via SharePoint access and Email under non-disclosure agreements for evaluation purposes. Depending on system configuration, anonymised review information may be made available to applicants.

Given their confidential and competitive nature, open call application data will not be made publicly accessible. Processing is conducted in accordance with the project Privacy Policy, applicable institutional rules, and GDPR.

2.4. Research and Sensitive Data

PERFORMANCE will generate empirical research data through qualitative and quantitative research activities.

Qualitative data will be generated through interviews, focus groups, workshops, and observations, and may include:

- Audio recordings (.wav, .mp3);
- Transcripts (.docx, .txt, .pdf);
- Fieldnotes and observation notes;
- Workshop materials;
- Video recordings (.mp4), where applicable.

Quantitative data will be generated through a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and related survey activities, including:

- Survey datasets (.csv, .xlsx, .sav);
- Experimental design files (.csv, .xlsx);
- Statistical analysis scripts (e.g., R, Stata);
- Codebooks and variable definitions (.pdf, .docx).

These datasets may contain personal data, including participants' professional roles, opinions, and experiences. All research involving human participants will be conducted on the basis of prior approval by the relevant Research Ethics Committees.

Personal data will be processed in accordance with GDPR and applicable national legislation. Research data will be pseudonymised at the earliest possible stage and stored on secure servers managed by the coordinating institution. Access will be restricted to authorised project researchers.

Due to their sensitive nature, raw research data containing personal information will not be made openly accessible outside the consortium.

At the time of this DMP version (Month 6), data collection has not yet been completed and final participant numbers cannot be specified. Estimated volumes of qualitative interviews, survey responses, and open call applications will be defined once recruitment procedures are finalised. The DMP will be updated accordingly to include indicative data volumes and storage requirements in the next revision.

2.5. Communication, Dissemination and Participatory Activity Data

PERIFORMANCE will generate and process data related to communication, dissemination, outreach, and participatory activities (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication).

This category includes data collected and produced in the context of workshops, webinars, training sessions (including train-the-trainer activities), interviews, focus groups, public events, stakeholder consultations, and other engagement activities. The data may comprise:

- Registration and attendance data (e.g., name, institutional affiliation, professional role, contact details);
- Professional profile information used for stakeholder mapping and invitations;
- Audio or video recordings of events (where applicable);
- Photographs or screenshots from events (online or onsite);
- Written contributions, comments, chat discussions, survey responses, and feedback forms;
- Aggregated summaries, reports, best practices, success stories, and derived conclusions produced for dissemination and reporting purposes;
- Communication metrics and KPIs (e.g., number of participants, website visits, webinar views, social media engagement statistics).

For communication and dissemination activities involving workshops, interviews, focus groups or similar events, informed consent will always be obtained prior to the collection, use, or sharing of any personal data. Participants will be clearly informed about:

- The purpose of the activity;
- The type of data that may be collected (including personal data, comments, audio/video recordings, images, and derived conclusions);
- The intended communication or dissemination channels (e.g., project reports, website, newsletters, social media, policy briefs, scientific publications).
- Contact details of the responsible consortium partner in case participants want to withdraw their consent.

No personal data, identifiable statements, photographs, or recordings will be used for communication or dissemination purposes without the explicit permission of the individuals concerned. Where appropriate, data will be anonymised or pseudonymised prior to publication or sharing to protect participants' privacy. Aggregated or fully anonymised summaries will be used whenever possible.

In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), limited personal data of relevant professional profiles (e.g., name, institutional affiliation, professional role, and contact details) may be processed and shared within the consortium solely for the purpose of identifying and inviting potential participants to project activities. Such processing will be based on a valid legal ground (e.g., legitimate interest or prior consent), will be proportionate and limited to what is necessary for the specified purpose, and will follow data minimisation principles. Appropriate safeguards, transparency measures, and information notices will be provided to data subjects.

All processing activities under this data category will comply with applicable data protection legislation, including the GDPR, relevant national laws, and institutional policies. Data will be stored securely, with access restricted to authorised project partners, and retained only for as long as necessary to fulfil the purposes of communication, dissemination, reporting, and audit obligations under Horizon Europe.

3. FAIR DATA

PERIFORMANCE implements the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) in accordance with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and Open Science obligations. The level of openness applied to each dataset is proportionate to its nature and subject to legal, ethical, confidentiality, and intellectual property constraints. Data will be made available following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.”

This approach does not apply to two of the data categories described above, namely **Administrative and Consortium Data** and **Open Call Application Data**, which contain data of no relevance to the Open Science mission. These datasets will not be made openly accessible and will be processed, stored, and retained strictly in line with contractual, legal, data protection, and confidentiality obligations.

3.1. Making Data Findable, Including Provisions for Metadata

Scientific publications and, where applicable and possible, associated datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that assign persistent identifiers. Public datasets and publications deposited in trusted repositories will remain available for a minimum of 10 years after project completion, in accordance with repository policies.

Persistent Identifiers

- Scientific publications will receive a DOI via the publishing Open Access journal or repository.
- Research datasets will be deposited in Zenodo (OpenAIRE-compliant).
- Deposited outputs will receive a DOI and be registered within OpenAIRE-compliant systems.

This ensures that publications and datasets are uniquely identifiable, citable, and persistently findable.

Metadata

Rich metadata will be provided in accordance with repository standards (e.g. DataCite, Dublin Core or equivalent schemas). Metadata will include:

- Title
- Authors and contributors
- Project acronym and Grant Agreement number
- Abstract
- Keywords
- Methodological description
- Data type and format
- Licensing conditions
- Version number
- Date of publication
- Persistent identifier (DOI)

3.2. Making Data Accessible

Repository and Access Mechanisms

Open datasets and publications will be deposited in:

- Zenodo (OpenAIRE-recognised repository);

This repository

- Assigns DOIs;
- Ensures persistent access;
- Provides access via standardised open protocols (e.g. HTTPS).

Identifiers resolve to digital objects and enable standard citation.

Access Conditions

Open Data

- Scientific publications will be made available in Open Access under a CC BY licence or equivalent.
- Non-sensitive datasets will be made available under standard open licences (e.g. CC0 or CC BY), in line with the Grant Agreement.

Restricted Data

Qualitative datasets (e.g. interviews, focus groups, fieldnotes, observations) and other datasets containing personal or sensitive data will not be publicly shared. Restrictions are based on:

- GDPR compliance;
- Ethical approvals and informed consent conditions;
- Legitimate interests of participants;
- Risk of re-identification, particularly in small expert communities.

Such data will be accessible only to authorised research team members based on the informed consent of the individuals participating in the study and stored securely on institutional servers. No Data Access Committee is foreseen, as sensitive data will not be shared externally.

If necessary, short embargo periods may be applied to non-sensitive datasets to allow publication of results.

Metadata Accessibility

Metadata will remain openly available, even where the underlying data are restricted, and will be licensed under CC0 unless legal or contractual constraints prevent this. Metadata records will include information on access conditions and contact details where relevant.

Where specific software is required to access datasets (e.g. statistical scripts), relevant documentation and, where possible, open-source code will be provided.

3.3. Making Data Interoperable

PERIFORMANCE will ensure interoperability by using established formats, standards, and documentation practices.

- Data will be stored in widely used, non-proprietary formats (e.g. .csv, .txt, .pdf).
- Quantitative datasets (e.g. DCE data) will include structured variable naming conventions and comprehensive codebooks.
- Metadata will follow recognised schemas (e.g. DataCite, Dublin Core, repository standards).
- Widely recognised terminology relevant to EU Open Science and research governance contexts will be applied.

Where project-specific categories or conceptual frameworks are developed (e.g. engagement typologies), they will be clearly documented and, where feasible, mapped to existing frameworks to facilitate reuse.

Datasets and publications will include qualified references (via DOIs) to related project outputs, ensuring internal and external linkages.

3.4. Increasing Data Re-use

PERIFORMANCE will provide sufficient documentation to allow validation of findings and facilitate reuse of non-sensitive datasets.

Documentation

For shareable datasets, the following will be provided:

- Readme files;
- Codebooks and variable definitions;
- Methodology descriptions;
- Data cleaning and processing procedures;
- Analysis scripts (where possible);
- Version information.

Quantitative datasets will be anonymised prior to sharing. Qualitative data containing personal information will not be reusable due to confidentiality and ethical restrictions.

Licensing and Long-Term Use

Open datasets will be released under standard reuse licences (e.g. CC BY, CC0), in line with Horizon Europe requirements. This will enable reuse by third parties, including beyond the project's lifetime, subject to licence terms.

Provenance will be documented through:

- Persistent identifiers (DOIs);
- Authorship and contributor records;
- Version control;
- Transparent methodological reporting.

Quality Assurance

Data quality will be ensured through:

- Standardised interview and survey protocols;
- Ethical oversight and compliance with approved research procedures;
- Internal review and coordination across work packages;
- Consistency checks prior to dataset publication;

- Peer review of scientific outputs.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Adequate human, technical, and financial resources are allocated to ensure the proper implementation of data management activities throughout the lifetime of PERIFORMANCE and, where applicable, beyond the project duration.

Governance and Responsibilities

Data management responsibilities are shared among consortium partners under the coordination of the project coordinator. Each Work Package (WP) leader is responsible for ensuring that data generated within their WP are managed in compliance with this Data Management Plan (DMP), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), relevant national legislation, and applicable institutional policies.

Data and know-how generated within the project will be classified and documented according to defined confidentiality levels and ethical requirements. Detailed provisions concerning data ownership, access rights, confidentiality obligations, and dissemination procedures are governed by the Consortium Agreement. Ownership of project results is defined in the Consortium Agreement. Each beneficiary owns the results it generates, unless otherwise agreed, and access rights are granted as specified in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

A structured coordination approach across participating organisations ensures:

- Compliance with FAIR principles;
- Adherence to ethical and legal requirements;
- Consistent documentation and curation practices;
- High data quality standards;
- Long-term value and impact of PERIFORMANCE research outputs.

Technical Infrastructure

The consortium operates a shared, secure data management environment to support:

- Day-to-day project operations;
- Internal communication and document exchange;
- Storage of research data and administrative documentation.

This infrastructure consists of institutional secure servers and/or project-level cloud-based platforms compliant with GDPR and institutional security standards. Access is password-protected and restricted to authorised users only, based on role and responsibility. Sensitive research data are stored on secure institutional servers with appropriate technical and organisational safeguards.

Procedures for data storage, backup, version control, preservation, and dissemination are defined at consortium level. Criteria for determining which data may be made publicly available are based on legal, ethical, confidentiality, and intellectual property considerations.

Human and Financial Resources

Resources allocated to data management include:

- Personnel time for data documentation, curation, anonymisation, and quality control;
- Preparation of metadata and repository submissions;
- Maintenance of secure storage and backup systems;
- Preparation of documentation to facilitate reuse (e.g. codebooks, readme files, methodological descriptions).

The following cost categories are foreseen and covered within the project budget:

- Repository deposition fees, where applicable;
- Secure cloud storage and server infrastructure;
- Transcription services for qualitative research data;
- Long-term archiving and preservation services.

All costs related to data management and Open Science compliance are included in the Horizon Europe grant budget. No additional external funding is required for the implementation of the measures described in this DMP.

5. DATA SECURITY AND ETHICAL COMPLIANCE

PERIFORMANCE implements comprehensive technical and organisational measures to ensure secure data processing and full compliance with applicable legal and ethical requirements. All personal data are processed in accordance with:

- The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR);
- Applicable national law;

- Applicable institutional data protection policies;
- The ethical requirements described in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Open Science Principles

Data security and ethical compliance are continuously monitored throughout the project, including oversight by the responsible Data Protection Officer (DPO).

5.1.Data Security Measures

Secure Storage and Access Control

The consortium uses a secure, shared cloud-based data management platform (SharePoint) to support internal project operations and research data storage. Depending on data sensitivity, storage is provided via:

- Secure BBMRI-ERIC servers;
- Institutional secure cloud infrastructure compliant with GDPR and institutional security standards.

Access to digital data is:

- Password-protected;
- Restricted to authorised personnel only;
- Managed through role-based access control.
- Possible only through two-factor authentication identification

Sensitive data are stored separately from identifying information. Unique participant identifiers are assigned to research participants to prevent direct identification.

Paper-based documents (e.g. signed consent forms) are stored in secure locked cabinets at consortium partners' locations with controlled physical access.

Pseudonymisation and Data Minimisation

Personal research data are pseudonymised at the earliest possible stage. Identification keys are stored separately from research data and accessible only to authorised personnel.

Only data strictly necessary to achieve the research objectives are collected, in accordance with the principle of data minimisation.

Sensitive qualitative research data will never appear in scientific publications, reports, or publicly shared datasets.

Data Recovery, Backup, and Long-Term Preservation

Technical safeguards include regular backups, secure data transfer protocols (e.g. encrypted connections), and institutional recovery procedures to prevent data loss.

Data selected for long-term preservation (e.g. anonymised quantitative datasets, publications, and public deliverables) will be deposited locally on secure servers as described above and in trusted repositories that ensure:

- Persistent identifiers (DOIs);
- Long-term preservation and curation;
- Appropriate access controls where required.

Sensitive personal data will not be deposited in public repositories and will continue to be protected in accordance with legal and ethical requirements.

Retention and Deletion Policy

Retention periods for qualitative research data are defined in respective study protocols and comply with applicable legal and ethical requirements:

- **Audio recordings:** Deleted one year after completion of analysis.
- **Pseudonymized transcripts and fieldnotes:** Retained for ten (10) years following completion of the research and then permanently deleted.

Deletion procedures follow secure institutional protocols to ensure irreversible removal of personal data.

5.2. Ethical Compliance

Ethical Approval and Oversight

Qualitative research involving human participants is conducted in accordance with the respective study protocols and subject to prior ethical approval by the relevant Research Ethics Committees, as required.

The project operates under Data Protection Officer oversight to ensure continued compliance with GDPR and national legislation.

Any substantial modification of research procedures will be assessed for ethical implications and, where necessary, submitted for additional ethical review.

Informed Consent and Participant Rights

Written informed consent is obtained from all research participants prior to data collection. Consent procedures clearly inform participants about:

- The purpose of the research;
- Recording procedures (including audio recording, where applicable);
- Types of data collected;
- Data storage duration and retention periods;
- Confidentiality safeguards;
- Conditions for data sharing (where applicable);
- The right to withdraw and applicable withdrawal timelines.
- Contact details of the data processor

Participants are also provided with privacy notices explaining their data protection rights under GDPR.

Participants retain the right to withdraw from the study within the limits defined in the informed consent documentation and applicable legal provisions.

Communication and dissemination activities

Communication, dissemination and participatory activity data that may be used for communication or dissemination purposes based on explicit prior consent from the individuals involved.

In such cases, a dedicated consent form will be prepared to clearly outline the objective of the communication activity, specify the categories of data that may be processed (such as name, professional role, individual contributions or comments, audio and/or video recordings, images, and any resulting summaries or conclusions), and identify the intended dissemination channels (including reports, project websites, social media platforms, newsletters, or scientific publications). Under no circumstances will personally identifiable information, quotations, photographs, or recordings be published or otherwise shared without the participant's documented authorization.

Ethical Considerations Affecting Data Sharing

Due to the nature of qualitative and stakeholder-based research conducted within PERIFORMANCE, several ethical and legal considerations limit data sharing:

- GDPR requirements;
- Ethical approval conditions;
- Legitimate interests and expectations of participants;
- Risk of re-identification, particularly in small expert or governance communities.

For these reasons, qualitative datasets (e.g. interviews, focus groups, fieldnotes, observations) will not be shared outside the consortium. Only aggregated, fully anonymized results and non-identifiable data will be disseminated.

Explicit consent from participants of engagement activities will be obtained for communicating or showcasing the outcomes within dissemination activities. However, no such exception will apply in the case of vulnerable groups or very small communities where the risk of identification, stigmatization, or unintended harm remains significant, even with consent, and in such cases stricter confidentiality safeguards will be maintained.

In certain cases, to further minimize any risk of identification, aggregated findings may be presented through the use of constructed “personas,” which illustrate the diversity of experiences, roles, or resources identified in the research while ensuring that no real individual’s personal data, statements, or identity can be inferred.

5.3.Pseudonymisation of Qualitative Research Data

Qualitative research data (including interviews, focus groups, workshops, and observations) will be processed in accordance with the study protocols and applicable data protection legislation.

All qualitative data will be pseudonymised at the earliest possible stage. Participants will be assigned a unique, non-identifying participant number. Direct identifiers (e.g. names, affiliations, contact details) will be removed from transcripts and stored separately from research data. Identification keys will be accessible only to authorised members of the study team.

Electronic documents (e.g. audio recordings, transcripts, fieldnotes) will be stored securely and password-protected on BBMRI-ERIC servers or its secure cloud service. Paper documents (e.g. signed consent forms) will be stored in secure locked facilities with restricted physical access.

Given the nature of the study, which may involve persons operating within small communities, there remains a potential risk of indirect identification. To mitigate this risk:

- Personal identifiers will be removed from transcripts wherever possible;
- Sensitive comments will be treated confidentially;
- Quotations may be masked, paraphrased, or excluded if there is a reasonable risk of identification;
- Participants may request the exclusion of specific statements, phrases, or comments;
- Where reasonably possible, such content will be removed from transcripts and, if feasible, edited out of original recordings;
- Excluded material will not be included in analysis or publications.

Participants will be informed of these procedures prior to consent and retain the right to withdraw from the study. Data that cannot be attributed to identifiable individuals (e.g. aggregated workshop outputs) or data already incorporated into published analyses cannot be retrospectively removed.

Raw qualitative data will not be shared outside the consortium. Only aggregated findings and non-identifiable excerpts will be included in publications and public deliverables.

Retention periods are defined as follows:

- Audio recordings: permanently deleted one year after completion of analysis.
- Transcripts and fieldnotes: retained for ten (10) years following completion of analysis to enable scientific reporting and verification, and then permanently deleted.

All processing of pseudonymised data complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and applicable national law.

